

Table continued

Culture	Hills infested (%)			Reaction ^a
	1978	1979	1980	
WGL22585	—	—	2	R
IET2895/RP9-4	—	0	—	R
RD9	1	0	—	R
BKN6806-46-60	2	0	—	R
B1047d-Kn-1-2-2-3	18	33	—	S
<i>Muey Nahng 62 M</i>				
Muey Nahng 62 M	0	6	26	S
<i>Muey Nahng 62 M/Eswarakora</i>				
BKNBR1030-11-2	0	6	6	MR
Siam 29				
Siam 29	14	0	—	MR
Siam 29 (ACC5915)	—	—	37	S
Siam 29 (ACC5473)	—	—	45	S
Siam 29 (ACC5916)	—	—	32	S
Siam 29 (ACC42)	—	—	18	S
Siam 29 (ACC36665)	—	—	32	S
RP6-17	0	0	0	R
W6L13400	0	0	0	R
CR189-4	2	0	—	R
OB677				
OB677	0	0	0	R
75-159	0	0	—	R
BG401-2	—	—	0	R
<i>Ptb/Siam 29</i>				
IR4744-123-1-3	3	11	—	MR
IR8 (susceptible check)	26	12	—	S
Jaya (susceptible check)	—	25	21	S
Tella hamsa (susceptible check)	—	—	44	S

^aBased on highest infestation over 3-year period. Resistant (R) = 0-5%; moderately resistant (MR) = 6-15%; susceptible (S) = 16% or more. ^bNo data available.

basis at 30 and 50 days after transplanting. The data represent the highest replications (see table).

Accessions of Siam 29, a prominent donor for many resistant cultures, were susceptible to gall midge. Its derivatives

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WGL13400 (Surekha) and RP6-17 (Phalguna) were resistant and are popular varieties in the region. Eswarakora derivatives W1263 and Kakatiya, originated at Warangal, were resistant while the exotic B1047d-kn-1-2-2-3 (Pelita 1/Eswarakora) was susceptible. Leuang 152 and OB677 were resistant. Leuang 152 derivatives reacted differently. CR95-JR-46-1 was resistant, while CR95-JR-214 was moderately resistant. Muey Nahng 62 M was susceptible. All Ptb derivatives except IR36 were resistant. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Productive nodal panicles after severe water stress

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The production of a second or nodal panicle from the primary tiller after water stress at the flowering period has been observed in rice. IR7790-18-1-2 produced a second panicle from the penultimate node of the main culm after a 10-day drought at the onset of flowering of the primary panicle (Fig. 1). The nodal panicles flowered about 60 days after partial or total desiccation of the primary panicles. Side tillers also flow-

1. Second nodal flowering pattern in rice after drought, IIRRI.

ered at almost the same time as the nodal panicles. These side tillers developed from the most basal node of the main culm (Fig. 2). Total computed yield (0.3 t/ha) was derived mainly from nodal panicles (0.2 t/ha) and side tiller panicles (0.1 t/ha). Primary panicles yielded a comparatively low 0.02 t/ha.

The importance of nodal tiller pani-

cles is questionable, but they may have economic implications in dryland rainfed areas, especially where the rainy season is long but variable at anthesis. Subsistence farmers could benefit from seed production for next season's crop. Any yield in the event of a severe drought at flowering would benefit food and seed production. ■

2. Second nodal panicle and side tiller panicle on drought-stressed rice plant. IRRI.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Response of IR8 to zinc fertilizer

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Zinc is considered an important limiting nutritional factor in Bangladesh rice production, especially where lands remain wet for long periods of the year and in calcareous soil zones. A simple fertilizer trial was carried out in a non-calcareous dark grey floodplain soil (order Inceptisol, suborder Aquept, and Subgroup Aeris Haplaquept) at BAU farm during the 1980 spring season.

IR8 was the test crop. Soil character-

istics were pH 6.3, organic carbon 1.67%, and available zinc 0.11 ppm. Treatments were control (no zinc application), application of 10 kg ZnSO₄/ha, and root-dipping in 2% ZnO suspension before transplanting.

At early growth stage, plants became stunted and tillering was reduced in the control plots. Growth in the zinc-treated plots was relatively better. Affected

plants recovered partially at a later growth stage but plant maturity was delayed by about 2 weeks. Although yields were relatively low in all plots, zinc application produced a marked yield increase over control (see table). The highest grain yield was recorded in ZnSO₄ treatment (130% increase over control). ■

Effect of zinc fertilizer on rice yield^a at Mymensingh, Bangladesh.

Treatment	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)	Increase (%) over control	Straw yield ^b (t/ha)	Increase (%) over control
ZnSO ₄	2.04	130	3.04	112
ZnO	1.94	118	2.74	91
Control	0.89	—	1.44	—

^aAv of 3 replications. ^bOven-dry basis.

Pest management and control DISEASES

Observations on diseases of dryland rice in Brazil, March 1981

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Goinia (Goias), Campinas (São Paulo), and Cuiaba (Mato Grosso), extensive rice areas in central southeastern Brazil were visited by a traveling workshop on blast and dryland rice and monitoring tour of large dryland rice areas in Brazil. The workshop-tour was jointly organized by the Brazilian Government (CNPAP, Goiania, and EMPA, Cuiaba-MT), Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical (CIAT, Colombia), and

the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) 12-19 March 1981.

The highly mechanized direct-seeded rice crop grown in acidic (pH about 4.0 to 5.0) soils with low water retention was found to be infected with varying severity by a number of fungal diseases. In the large rice areas in Mato Grosso, disease incidence was high (see table). In general, rice was in grain ripening or maturity stages and in some cases was being harvested. Diseases recorded were foliar blast, neck blast (*Pyricularia oryzae*), narrow brown leaf spot (*Sphaerulina oryzae*), leaf scald (*Rhynchosporium oryzae*), stack burn (*Alternaria padwickii*), sheath rot (*Acrocyndrium oryzae*), sheath blight (*Thanatephorus cucumeris*), and brown spot (*Helminthosporium oryzae*).

Because of a long drought (about 25 days), the crop in Campinas was generally poor and foliar blast was either absent or in a mild form. No other disease was observed. In uniform blast nursery trials, however, foliar blast was severe in irrigated crops.

Observations at the sites visited led to these conclusions:

- Three varieties under extensive cul-